

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION AND THEIR DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the digital technologies in education and their didactic opportunities from a scientific-theoretical perspective. It discusses the role, advantages, types, and the contribution of digital technologies in improving the effectiveness of the educational process. Furthermore, the paper provides an analysis of the classification of digital educational technologies, the practical aspects of their integration into the pedagogical process, and highlights the challenges in this area with corresponding conclusions.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, didactic opportunities, digital education, pedagogical software tools, multimedia technologies, interactive exercises, mobile learning, virtual technologies, artificial intelligence.*

INTRODUCTION. By the 21st century, digital technologies have rapidly developed across all sectors worldwide, producing unprecedented innovations. Studying foreign advanced experiences, introducing international standards into our educational system, and making extensive use of digital technologies are critical for the educational process. The use of digital technologies in education has already shown positive results internationally. For our educational system to achieve high results, digital products in digital formats must be employed. Modern technologies implemented in education should primarily serve to elevate the quality of education to a new level.

Creating an information-rich educational environment, widely introducing multimedia applications targeted at specific educational subjects, and aligning the base of educational-methodological materials for secondary schools with international standards for education quality assessment systems are key priorities in the development of Uzbekistan's education system, according to the "Concept for the Development of the National Education System of Uzbekistan by 2030." This includes the use of interactive electronic learning resources to improve historical literacy, scientific worldview, and key competencies in history lessons and extracurricular activities.

In the context of continuous education, it is vital to assimilate modern information and communication technologies and digital telecommunication methods, which not only define the current level of development but are now deeply embedded in every aspect of society, from schools and universities to daily family life. [7]

METHODOLOGY. As society transitions to digitalization, the educational system must adapt and leverage the advantages of this transition. To achieve this, it is necessary to train creative and digitally skilled individuals who can work with advanced technologies.

O. Musurmanova discusses the process of developing the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies of specialists through pedagogical technologies, as well as the features of organizing the stages of education, and the social, philosophical, methodological, didactic, pedagogical,

psychological, physiological, hygienic, ideological, legal, economic, historical, scientific-theoretical, and methodological foundations for implementing educational technologies. [2]

A group of specialists emphasize that successful informatization of education requires meeting three essential conditions:

- Technological: the availability, reliability, and ease of use of digital technologies, as well as the robust technological infrastructure of the digital education environment.

- Organizational-methodological: the alignment of the use of digital technologies with clear educational goals, the availability of organizational conditions, and the availability and quality of digital educational resources.

- Human resources: the readiness and ability of educators to work effectively in a digital education environment, using new methods and forms, with support from administration, parents, and the broader community. [3]

Improving and popularizing teaching through modern information communication technologies, as well as deeply studying the experiences of developed countries in electronic education technologies, undoubtedly leads to an increase in educational effectiveness. [8]

Currently, all educational institutions pay special attention to the use of innovative technologies in the educational environment to ensure that students acquire knowledge aligned with modern requirements. In particular, the role and importance of interactive pedagogical software tools in creating electronic publications of educational resources are significant. Examples of such resources include digital textbooks, e-learning manuals, audio and video lessons, control assignments, non-standard digital tests, catalogs, and various programs that create interactive exercises.

The effective use of modern information communication technologies in education has been investigated in Uzbekistan in the following directions: the implementation of pedagogical and information technologies in higher education practices by A. Abduqodirov, N. Azizkhodjaeva, U. Sh. Begimqulov, R. X. Djuraev, Sh. Sharipov; effective use of interactive and pedagogical software tools in education by G. S. Ergashova, Sh. Pozilova; preparation of students for professional activities based on software tools by S. J. Turayev, M. A. Artikova, M. A. Batirov, D. N. Rahmatov; and the creation and use of digital educational resources by L. M. Umarov, B. Suropov, L. M. Qaraxonova, B. S. Samandarov, N. O. Rakhimov, F. H. Gaffarov, S. Q. Tursunov, M. Fayziyeva, S. Rahmatova. However, pedagogical software tools and their didactic opportunities in the educational process have yet to be fully explored.

Foreign scholars D. M. Al-Hezam, P. Andersson, A. Balanskat, A. Balyer, A. W. Bates, K. A. Bingimlas, K. Fielding, D. Ifenthaler, Y. Jang, J. Bersin, M. Christian, N. Negroponte, R. Puente-Dura, B. Rott, N. Selwyn, J. T. Schmidt, S. Chauhan, V. Gregory, E. C. Wenger, W. Aaron, P. Mell, R. Miller, M. Rause, and F. Tao have contributed to the theoretical and methodological aspects of implementing digital technologies in the educational process, educational platforms, and the integration of digital education resources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the context of the credit-modular system, organizing the educational process through digital educational technologies and pedagogical software tools is one of the most promising directions. Preparing educational materials using modern software tools in higher education expands the opportunities of students. Therefore, it is important to develop competencies in using digital educational technologies to foster professional and creative skills in future educators.

Next, we define the concept of digital education and digital learning environments: Digital technologies are a broad concept that includes various technologies using digital data and algorithms for processing information and automating tasks. They allow for efficient collection, storage, processing, and transmission of data. [4]

Digital educational technologies refer to the use of digital tools and resources to enhance the educational process and organize a digital learning environment. They include tools, software, and online resources that help improve the convenience, effectiveness, and quality of education. [6]

Digital educational technologies refer to the use of modern information communication technologies (ICT), internet platforms, multimedia tools, and software in education to effectively organize the teaching and learning process. [9]

Digital education technologies are those that support the digitization of the learning experience and facilitate the transition to online learning. Educational technologies, by definition, include any communication, information, and technological tools that help improve teaching, development, and assessment. This includes computer equipment (e.g., interactive boards, tablets for educational activities), software (from streaming to gamification), and theories and practices of education (such as lifelong learning or nanoeducation), along with innovations in educational technologies that continue to transform the learning environment. [11]

Digitalization of education refers to the transition to an electronic teaching system where all educational materials, manuals, and assignments are available online. [10]

Digital didactics is a branch of pedagogy that focuses on organizing the educational process in a digital environment. It involves studying, enhancing, and modifying the key concepts and principles of traditional didactics to align with the digital environment.

The core principles of digital education include:

- The personalization principle
- The goal-oriented principle
- The flexibility principle
- The success principle
- The collaborative learning principle
- The practice-oriented principle
- The principle of increasing complexity
- The saturation principle of the learning environment
- The polymodal (multimedia) principle
- The assessment principle.

The classification of digital educational technologies has been widely studied in scientific research. Scholars have grouped these technologies into categories based on different criteria to better integrate them into the educational process. Below is a classification based on the most widely used categories.

In her research, S. Rahmatova defines the modern digital educational environment as encompassing the following: collections, information arrays, educational portals, websites, telecommunications, management systems, and both personal and collective information spaces [10].

M.Abdullaxo‘jayeveva lists the following types of digital educational technologies:

1. **Digital educational content** - creating electronic textbooks, educational websites, and media applications.
2. **Educational communication networks** - developing communication systems between students, teachers, and educational institutions through various platforms and online resources.
3. **Mobile education** - extensive use of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets, laptops) in the learning process.
4. **Gamification** - integrating virtual game elements into education.
5. **Cloud technologies** - methods for remotely storing, distributing, and processing data [5].

In the course of our research, we identified that the following types of digital educational technologies yield effective results in the preparation of future history teachers and the development of their professional and creative abilities.

Table 1

Digital technologies in education and their didactic opportunities

Technology	Classification	Digital learning tools	Didactic Possibilities
Multimedia technologies	Audio and video materials	Audio texts (e-books) Videos (feature and documentary films, shows)	Documentary films, podcasts, and audio stories can be presented to showcase historical events and occurrences in a vivid and engaging manner.
	Interactive presentations	"Microsoft PowerPoint", "Google Slides", "Prezi", "Keynote", "Mentimeter", "Socrative", "Kahoot" Canva Genially	These tools allow the addition of questions, animations, graphics, and many other interactive elements (games). Additionally, they provide the ability to depict historical periods, maps, and events.
	Animation	VideoScribe Animaker Canva	It allows for the dynamic explanation of historical processes.
	Graphics and infographics creation tools	Canva PosterMyWall Pictochart Vengagge Visme	It enables the visualization of information through historical maps, images, and diagrams.
Interactive exercises and game-based technologies	Game-based learning platforms.	Kahoot! Quizizz! Mentimeter wordwall	Technologies designed to enhance student engagement and educational productivity by incorporating game elements into the learning strategy.

	Interactive exercises.	CROSS Crosswordus Flippity " Crossword Puzzle Maker "" Edupics.com	It provides an opportunity to actively engage in the process of reinforcing historical knowledge, deeply studying events, and mastering the material.
Mobile learning technologies	M-learning	Mobile learning platforms and applications Interactive tests and quizzes Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR) Timelines and historical maps Historical podcasts and audiobooks Mobile museum and archive applications Collaboration applications	This allows the reception or presentation of data in any format to personal mobile devices. Through mobile applications and devices, learning can take place anytime and anywhere.
Software product development technologies	AutoPlay Media Studio ISpring Hot Potatoes	Electronic educational resources	Creating multimedia interactive teaching-methodological guides and electronic educational resources
Virtual technologies	Virtual Reality (VR)	Virtual Tours	Students can take virtual trips around the world to museums, historical landmarks, and various places without leaving their classrooms.
		Collaboration	Virtual reality allows students to collaborate on projects in real-time, regardless of their geographical location.
	Virtual augmented reality	Interactive textbooks	Using AR, textbooks can be enriched with interactive 3D models, animations, and videos, making the learning material more engaging and easier to understand.
		Game mechanics	AR can be used to create game scenarios that motivate students

			and make learning more engaging and interactive.
Intelligent educational systems	Artificial intelligence-based systems	ChatGPT, GPT-4, Siri, Alexa	A field of science and technology focused on creating machines capable of mimicking human intelligence.
	Chatbots	Google Assistant History Bot	These are programs or systems designed to interact with users, answering questions or engaging in simple conversations with them.
Cloud technologies	Google cloud services	Text documents Spreadsheets Presentations	It is a new service that involves remote access to data processing and storage tools.
Online collaboration tools		Google Docs, Miro, Padlet	These tools allow students to collaborate on historical projects in real-time, exchange documents, and communicate with their peers and teachers.
Assessment and feedback tools	Interactive tests and exercises	Google Forms, Quizizz, Kahoot	Students will have the opportunity to assess and analyze their knowledge in a digital format. These technologies allow for the creation of historical tests and surveys, with automatic evaluation of their results.

CONCLUSION

In today's society, as it transitions to a digital system, the education sector must also adapt and effectively utilize the advantages of this transformation. To achieve this, it is necessary to cultivate a workforce capable of working with advanced technologies and possessing digital skills, as well as fostering creative thinking [12]. In conclusion, it can be stated that an education process based on digital technologies helps to develop important competencies in students, such as independent thinking, problem analysis, and effective information management. At the same time, it creates the foundation for developing learners' digital culture, enabling them to become active digital citizens capable of participating in the global information space.

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